

INTERESTING GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS

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Abstract. In this article, we present to readers some information about some interesting geometric problems and their solution methods.

Keywords: circle, diameter, triangle, center.

Issue 1.

In a circle with center O, CD is perpendicular to the diameter AB. AE- watar OC bisects the radius. Prove it; The chord DE passes through the middle of the chord BC. Proof. Let the circle be ω . $CO \cap \omega = F \Rightarrow AF = BC = BD \Rightarrow AD = BF \Rightarrow \angle AED = \angle FCB \Rightarrow (M - CO \text{ the middle of and } DE \cap BC = N) \Rightarrow MNEC - \text{cycle} \Rightarrow \angle MEC = \angle MNC \quad \angle MEC = \angle AEC = \angle ABC = \angle MNC \Rightarrow MN \parallel OB \Rightarrow CN = NB \Rightarrow ?$

Issue 2.

ABCDE-pentagon ω is inscribed outside the circle. Prove that if BC intersects the circle ω at point K and $AB=BC=CD \quad \angle EKB = 90^\circ$

Proof. $LA = KC = KM = CP$ and $BK = BL = DP = DN \Rightarrow \angle KCP = \angle LAM$ and $\angle KBL = \angle PDK \Rightarrow KP = LM, KL = PN$ $KM = PL$ and $PL = KN \Rightarrow KM = KN$.

Point O is the center of the circle. $MO = OK = NO$ and $MK = KN \Rightarrow \angle MOK = \angle NOK \Rightarrow$

The straight line KO is the bisector of $\angle MON$, and so is the straight line EO . \Rightarrow

E, O, K – collinear $OK \perp BC \Rightarrow EK \perp BC \Rightarrow \angle EKB = 90^\circ \Rightarrow \blacktriangle$

Issue 3.

a, b, c are the sides of a triangle. If $c^4 = a^4 + b^4$, prove it; this triangle has an acute angle.

Proof. We use the theorem of cosines. $c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cdot \cos \alpha \Leftrightarrow c^4 = a^4 + b^4 + 2a^2b^2 - 4a^3b \cos \alpha - 4ab^3 \cos \alpha + 4a^2b^2(\cos \alpha)^2 \Leftrightarrow 2a^2b^2 + 4a^2b^2 \cos \beta = 4a^3b \cos \alpha + 4ab^3 \cos \alpha \Leftrightarrow ab + 2ab \cos \beta = 2a^2 \cos \alpha + 2b^2 \cos \alpha \Leftrightarrow ab = 2 \cos \alpha \cdot c^2 \Rightarrow \cos \alpha > 0 \Rightarrow \alpha < 90^\circ$. $a^2 = b^2 + c^2 - 2bc \cos \beta \Leftrightarrow a^4 = b^4 + c^4 + 4b^2c^2(\cos \beta)^2 - 4b^3c \cos \beta - 4bc^3 \cos \beta + 2b^2c^2 \Rightarrow 2b^4 + 4b^2c^2(\cos \beta)^2 + 2b^2c^2 - 4b^3c \cos \beta - 4bc^3 \cos \beta \Leftrightarrow b^3 + bc^2 = 2bc \cos \beta (b + c - c \cos \beta)$ $1 > \cos \beta \Rightarrow c - c \cos \beta > 0 \Rightarrow \cos \beta > 0 \Rightarrow \beta < 90^\circ$ just like that $\varphi < 90^\circ \Rightarrow \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0; \frac{\pi}{2}) \Rightarrow$ triangle with acute angles $\Rightarrow \blacktriangle$

Issue 4. $\angle A=90^\circ$ in $\triangle ABC$. The center of BC is point M, point D is taken from AC such that $AD=MA$. The second point of intersection of circles inscribed outside $\triangle AMC$ and $\triangle BDC$ is point P. Prove that straight line CP bisects $\angle BCA$.

Proof; Let P' be the center of the arc AM. \Rightarrow If $P'C$ bisects $\angle BCA \Rightarrow BCDP'$ is cyclic. $AD=MB, AP'=P'M, \angle BCA=2\alpha \Rightarrow \angle CAM=2\alpha$ and $\angle P'AM=\alpha \Rightarrow \angle DAP'=3\alpha \Rightarrow \angle P'MB=3\alpha$ and $AD=MB, AP'=P'M \Rightarrow \triangle ADP'=\triangle MP'B \Rightarrow \angle ADP'=\angle P'BM \Rightarrow CDP'B$ - cyclic $\Rightarrow P'=P \Rightarrow \blacktriangle$

Issue 5. BE and CF are altitudes in $\triangle ABC$. Point P is taken from inside BC. Point Q is the continuation of BC on side B. If $BQ^2 = BP^2 = BF \cdot AB$ and $QF \cap PE = S$, prove; Points A, E, F, C lie on 1 circle.

Proof.

$BE \cap CF = H \Rightarrow AH \perp BP, AH \cap BP = R, QPEA$ – we prove that it is cyclic. $\angle QAB = \angle BQF = \beta$. $QPEA$ – To prove cyclicity $CE \cdot CA = CP \cdot CQ$ it is enough to prove that. $CE \cdot CA = CR \cdot CB \Rightarrow CP \cdot CQ = CR \cdot CB$.

$CP \cdot (CB + BQ) = CP(CB + BP) = CR \cdot CB \Leftrightarrow CP(CB + BP) = (CP + PR) \cdot CB \Leftrightarrow CP \cdot BP = PR \cdot BC. \Leftrightarrow (BC - BP) \cdot BP = PR \cdot BC = (BP - BR) \cdot BC \Leftrightarrow -BP^2 = -BR \cdot BC$.

$BR \cdot BC = BF \cdot BA \Rightarrow BP^2 = BF \cdot BA$. This is given in the condition. $\Rightarrow AQPE$ – cyclic. $\angle AQF = x \Rightarrow \angle PEC = \angle AFS = \beta + x \Rightarrow AFSE \Rightarrow A, E, F, S$ points lie on the same circle. $\Rightarrow \blacktriangle$

Issue 6.

Let H be the point of intersection of the altitudes of acute-angled triangle ABC . The circle with its center in the middle of the side BC and passing through the point H intersects the straight line BC at the points A_1 and A_2 . Similarly, the circle with its center in the middle of the side CA and passing through the point H intersects the straight line CA at points B_1 and B_2 , and the circle AB with its center in the middle of the side AB and passing through the point H intersects the straight line at points C_1 and C_2 . Prove that points $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ lie on one circle.

Proof. The radius of the circle passing through the point H with its center in the middle of BC is R_1 and its center is O_1 . Similarly, let O_2, R_2 and O_3, R_3 .

$BC = 2a, AC = 2b$ and $AB = 2c \Rightarrow BC_2 = c - R_3$ and $BA_1 = a - R_1, BC_1 = c + R_3, BA_2 = a + R_1$. $O_1O_3 \parallel AC \Rightarrow O_1O_3 \perp BH$. $BH \cap AC = B' \Rightarrow O_3B' = c$ and $O_1B' = a$.

$O_3H = R_3$ and $O_1H = R_1$ According to Carnot's theorem, the following is appropriate; $B'O_3^2 - O_3H^2 = O_1B'^2 - O_1H^2 \Leftrightarrow c^2 - R_3^2 = a^2 - R_1^2 \Leftrightarrow (c - R_3) \cdot (c + R_3) = (a - R_1) \cdot (a + R_1) \Rightarrow BC_2 \cdot BC_1 = BA_1 \cdot BA_2 \Rightarrow A_1A_2C_1C_2$ – cyclic. Likewise $CA_2 \cdot CA_1 = CB_2 \cdot CB_1$ and $AC_1 \cdot AC_2 = AB_1 \cdot AB_2 \Rightarrow A_1A_2B_1B_2$ and $B_1B_2C_1C_2$ cyclic. $\Rightarrow A_1A_2B_1B_2C_1C_2$ hexagonal cyclic. $\Rightarrow A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ points lie on the same circle.

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